

Development of Lithium Battery Polymer Electrolyte Membrane with Lithium Perchlorate (LiClO₄) and Rice Ash Silica

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Abstract

The development of lithium batteries demands efficient, stable, and environmentally friendly electrolyte innovation. Polymer electrolyte membranes (MEPs) are now in the main focus because they offer high conductivity and a better level of safety than liquid electrolytes. This review discusses the role of lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄) and silica from rice husks (rice ash silica) as reinforcing agents in MEP. LiClO₄ was chosen for its ionic conductivity as well as good thermal and anode stability, while rice ash silica acts as a natural filler that improves the mechanical strength and thermal stability of the membrane. The combination of the two is proven to strengthen the polymer's structure and improve the electrochemical performance of the battery. In addition, the ion transfer mechanism, synthesis method, and the influence of composition ratio on physical properties and conductivity were also analyzed. Potential applications in solid lithium batteries and sustainability aspects are also discussed, summarizing future research trends and development opportunities for silica-based MEPs of rice ash silica and LiClO₄.

Keywords:

ionic conductivity, polymer membrane, natural filler, thermal stability, *solid-state battery*

1. Introduction

Increasing global energy needs are driving the development of efficient, lightweight, and safe energy storage systems. Lithium-ion batteries are the top choice thanks to their high energy density and long service life (Armand et al., 2008). However, the use of liquid electrolytes in these batteries poses a risk of fire and leakage, lowering their level of safety and

reliability. This challenge has triggered efforts to replace liquid electrolytes with polymer electrolyte membranes (MEPs) that offer better stability and safety (Karabelli et al., 2021).

Both synthetic and natural polymer-based MEPs have shown advantages in thermal stability, ease of production, and design flexibility (Permata et al., 2023). Polymers such as *polyethylene oxide* and

polyvinylidene fluoride are often used as matrices, but still face constraints on ionic conductivity and thermal degradation. Performance improvement efforts are carried out through the addition of lithium salts and inorganic fillers (Ravi & Jayaraj, 2022). Lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) is one of the most researched lithium salts due to its good solubility and ability to produce free lithium ions in polymer matrices (Ravi et al., 2025).

The addition of LiClO_4 to *polyethylene oxide polymers* has been shown to significantly improve ionic conductivity (Armand et al., 2008). Electrolyte stability remains a major challenge in lithium batteries (Lee et al., 2021), so the development of supporting materials such as silicon and polysulfone continues to be undertaken to improve the chemical stability and pore structure of the membrane (Chik et al., 2022). The study of Pan et al. (2021) showed that composite polymer electrolytes with propylene carbonate can be produced effectively and produce high ion conductivity. Inorganic fillers, particularly silica from rice ash, attract attention due to their amorphous structure, large surface area, and high silicon dioxide content. Rice ash silica plays a role in improving thermal stability, improving membrane morphology, and lowering polymer crystallinity, thereby

supporting ion diffusion in MEP (Ying., et al., 2018).

This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the development of lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) and silica rice ash MEPs, highlighting the material structure, synthesis methods, physical and electrochemical characteristics, and performance in lithium batteries. The references used are from the last five years of scientific publications that have been experimentally verified. This study seeks to answer several key questions: How does LiClO_4 and silica rice ash affect the electrochemical structure and performance of MEP? What is the most effective synthesis method to produce membranes with high conductivity and stability? What are the factors that determine the efficiency and sustainability of this material-based MEP system? By identifying the latest technical trends and challenges, it is hoped that an optimal strategy can be found for the development of a more efficient and stable polymer electrolyte membrane for future lithium battery systems.

2. Methodology

The methodology in this study is designed to examine and analyze scientific advances related to the strengthening of polymer electrolyte membranes (MEPs) based on lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) and

silica rice ash. The main focus lies in the characterization of materials using several techniques, namely *Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy* (FTIR) and *X-ray Diffraction* (XRD) to identify chemical structure and crystallinity levels. In addition, *Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy* (EIS) and *Cyclic Voltammetry* (CV) are used to evaluate the ionic conductivity and electrochemical stability of membranes. Thermal analysis is carried out with *Thermogravimetric Analysis* (TGA) and *Differential Scanning Calorimetry* (DSC) to assess the thermal stability of the material.

Studies examining the combination of lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) and rice ash silica in one system are a top priority. The commonly used synthesis method is the casting or solvent evaporation technique with variations in the composition of LiClO_4 between 15–25% and silica rice ash of 5–10% by weight per volume (w/v). This approach focuses on understanding the relationship between structure and performance through characterization, rather than on the details of the fabrication process. The synthesis of findings from various studies is the basis for evaluating the effectiveness of the combination of materials.

2.1 Working Principle of Lithium Battery

A lithium-ion battery consists of four main components: anode, cathode,

electrolyte, and separator. During charging, lithium ions move from the cathode to the anode through the electrolyte, while electrons flow through the external circuit from the cathode to the anode. At the time of use (discharging), the lithium ions return to the cathode and the electrons flow from the anode to the cathode, generating an electric current (Wong & Chow, 2020). This process is called intercalation, where lithium ions enter and exit the crystal structure of the electrode without damaging it. The function of the separator is to prevent direct contact between the anode and the cathode from short circuiting (Guo et al., 2021). The chemical reaction that takes place involves a redox reaction, in which the anode is oxidized and the cathode is reduced during discharging, while this process is reversed during charging (Wong & Chow, 2020).

Modern lithium-ion batteries operate through a Li^+ ion intercalation/deintercalation mechanism between the cathode and the anode. During charging, Li^+ ions migrate from the cathode (usually a coated compound such as NMC or LFP) to a graphite or lithium metal anode through an electrolyte, while electrons flow through an external circuit. This process reverses during

emptying (Noer, Z., & Dayana, I., 2021).

Research shows that polymer electrolyte membranes based on polyethylene oxide (PEO) and lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) with the addition of inorganic fillers such as silica (SiO_2) are able to achieve ionic conductivity in the range of 10^{-4} S/cm at room temperature (Alisy Rohma, 2023). Modification of the polymer matrix with the filler increases the migration path of lithium ions and decreases the crystallinity of the polymer, thereby improving the electrochemical performance of the membrane.

The addition of 15% by weight of rice ash silica to the polymer electrolyte membrane is able to reduce the crystallinity of polyethylene oxide (PEO) from about 45% to 28%, which has an impact on increasing ionic conductivity by up to 300% (Anggraeni, 2023). The mixing technique using ultrasound for 2 hours proved to be effective in increasing the homogeneity of silica particle dispersion in the polymer matrix, thereby improving ion mobility and membrane performance.

The synthesis of the working principle of lithium batteries is the basis for an important understanding in the development of electrolyte

membranes that are able to support the efficient and stable transfer of lithium ions.

2.2 Characteristics of Polymer Electrolyte Membrane

An effective polymer electrolyte membrane must have high ionic conductivity to support the efficient movement of lithium ions. For example, a polymer membrane cross-linked with unsaturated polyester is able to achieve an ionic conductivity of 1.99×10^{-3} S/cm at 30 °C, which supports the stable performance of lithium metal batteries (Liu, F. et al., 2020).

The membrane must also be resistant to high temperatures and have a wide window of electrochemical stability. Membranes with cross-linked structures exhibit thermal stability up to 150 °C and an electrochemical stability window of about 4.6 V, important to prevent degradation during the battery charge and discharge cycle (Liu, F. et al., 2020).

The flexibility and mechanical strength of the membrane need to be sufficient to resist deformation during battery operation. The polymer membrane based on poly(arylene ether sulfone)-graft-poly(ethylene glycol) has an elongation of up to 250% and dimensional stability of up to 120 °C,

making it suitable for battery applications (Kim, S. et al., 2019).

The transportation efficiency of lithium ions is measured by the lithium ion transport rate (t_{Li^+}). A good membrane should have a high t_{Li^+} to reduce polarization and improve battery efficiency. Modification of the polymer structure can improve the t_{Li^+} value and overall performance of the battery (Maia, B. A., et al., 2022).

Polymer electrolyte membranes (MEPs) have important characteristics that determine their performance in lithium batteries, especially when it comes to ionic conductivity and thermal stability. MEP structures generally consist of polymer matrices such as polyethylene oxide (PEO) or poly(vinylidene fluoride)-hexafluoropropylene (PVDF-HFP), lithium salts such as lithium perchlorate ($LiClO_4$) or lithium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI), as well as inorganic fillers such as silica (SiO_2) and alumina (Al_2O_3) that function to improve the mechanical and thermal stability of the membrane (Chen et al., 2020). The decrease in polymer crystallinity due to interaction with lithium salts and inorganic fillers opens up more efficient ionic pathways, thereby improving the free lithium ion mobility

and ionic conductivity of the membrane. In addition, the homogeneity of the dispersion of fillers in polymer matrices greatly affects electrochemical performance, where good mixing techniques such as ultrasonication can improve particle distribution and optimize the physical properties of the membrane (Chen et al., 2020). Thus, the physical and electrochemical characteristics of MEP are greatly influenced by the material composition and the synthesis method applied.

The synthesis of these polymer electrolyte membrane characteristics suggests that the combination of thermal, mechanical, and ionic conductivity stability is a key factor in the development of optimal MEPs.

2.3 Characteristics of Lithium perchlorate ($LiClO_4$)

Lithium perchlorate ($LiClO_4$) is known to have high ionic conductivity in various polymer matrices. Research by Sudiarti et al. (2017) showed that a cellulose acetate-based polymer membrane with the addition of 25% by weight of $LiClO_4$ achieved an ionic conductivity of 1.79×10^{-4} S/cm. Increased $LiClO_4$ concentrations can increase ionic conductivity until it reaches a certain optimum value.

LiClO₄ interacts with functional groups in the polymer matrix, such as carbonyl and ether groups, affecting the structure and mobility of ions in the polymer's electrolyte membrane. The Fullerton-Shirey, S. K., & Maranas, J. K. (2009) study reported that the addition of LiClO₄ to polyethylene oxide (PEO) lowered the glass transition temperature (T_g) and polymer crystallinity, thereby improving the mobility of lithium ions.

The thermal and electrochemical stability of LiClO₄ is also fairly good. Manap et al. (2019) found that the polymer membrane based on poly(L-lactic acid)-poly(propylene glycol) with LiClO₄ was stable up to a temperature of 270 °C. The wide window of electrochemical stability supports lithium-ion battery applications.

The addition of LiClO₄ in the polymer matrix can affect the mechanical properties of the membrane. Sudiarti et al. (2017) reported an increase in tensile strength from 19.89 MPa to 43.29 MPa and elongation from 2.55% to 4.53% at the addition of 10% LiClO₄ weight. LiClO₄ concentrations above 10% may decrease tensile strength even though elongation continues to increase.

This synthesis of lithium perchlorate characteristics confirms the important role of LiClO₄ in improving ionic conductivity and thermal stability while influencing the mechanical properties of the membrane.

2.4 Characteristics of Silica Rice Ash

Rice husk ash contains high levels of silica (SiO₂), which is between 94% and 96%, depending on the combustion conditions and refining process (Dewi et al., 2018). The high silica content makes rice husk ash a potential source of silica for a wide range of industrial applications.

The silica structure in rice husk ash can be amorphous or crystalline, depending on the combustion temperature. Combustion at a temperature of about 400 °C produces amorphous silica with a high surface area and good reactivity (Chandra et al., 2012). Higher combustion temperatures, such as 700–900 °C, convert silica into less reactive crystalline (Sari, K., et al., 2021).

Rice husk ash silica has significant porosity and water absorption. Grinding for 15 hours increased porosity from 6.0% to 10.7% and water absorption from 5.3% to 10.2% (Shanmugaraj, P., et al., 2019). The grinding process lowers the heat and

heat capacity of the type, indicating a change in the thermal properties of the material.

The silica particle size of rice husk ash is in the range of nanometers, between 25.1 to 40.6 nm, with a density of 0.6650 to 0.8120 g/mL (Dewi et al., 2018). Small size and fine morphology increase specific surface area, essential for applications as adsorbents or composite fillers.

The silica characteristics of rice husk ash, such as high silica content, amorphous structure, porosity, and nano particle size, make it an excellent material for applications as polymer electrolyte membrane fillers, heavy metal ion adsorbents, as well as raw materials for zeolite and ceramic manufacturing (Hastuti et al., 2020).

This synthesis of rice ash silica characteristics underscores its potential as a natural filler that improves the stability and performance of polymer electrolyte membranes.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Applications of Lithium Perchlorate (LiClO₄) in Lithium Batteries

Lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄) is a lithium salt that is often used as an electrolyte in polymer electrolyte membranes (MEPs) for lithium batteries. LiClO₄ has a high solubility

in organic solvents and is able to produce lithium ions (Li⁺) that move easily in the polymer matrix, thereby improving ionic conductivity (Wardhani, A. S.S, et al., 2017). The addition of LiClO₄ serves as a Li⁺ ion donor that supports ion transport through the segmentation of polymer chain motion.

The large, non-coordinating ClO₄⁻ anion helps maintain the thermal stability of the system, although its oxidative properties require special attention in humid environments. LiClO₄ tends to form complexes with polymer chains such as PEO or poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA), and solution mixing methods have been shown to result in an even distribution of LiClO₄ as well as stable conductivity in thermal cycle tests (Ginting, E. M., & Bukit, N., 2014).

The limitation of LiClO₄ as a single ingredient in MEP lies primarily in its long-term thermal stability. The combination of LiClO₄ with other materials such as rice ash silica is an effective strategy to improve the mechanical strength as well as thermal and electrochemical stability of the membrane. Lithium perchlorate plays an important role in improving the ionic conductivity and electrochemical stability of membranes, but it needs to

be combined with natural fillers to overcome the limitations of long-term thermal stability.

3.2 Application of Rice Ash Silica in Lithium Batteries

Silica from rice husk ash is a natural filler that has the potential to be used in the polymer electrolyte membrane (MEP) of lithium batteries. The high SiO₂ content, amorphous structure with large surface area, and nanoparticle size allow for improved mechanical and thermal stability of the membrane (Hastuti et al., 2020). Rice ash silica improves membrane morphology by strengthening polymer tissues and reducing excess crystallization in PEO-like matrices (Shanmugaraj, P., et al., 2019). The interaction between silica and polymers forms an ionic pathway that smooths the movement of lithium ions so that ionic conductivity increases (Dewi et al., 2018).

The high thermal properties of rice ash silica improve the membrane durability at the operating temperature of the battery, extending the life of the battery (Shanmugaraj, P., et al., 2019). The addition of silica also reduces water permeability, preventing electrolyte degradation due to moisture. Research by Hastuti et al. (2020) reported that the addition of 5% by weight of silica rice ash increased

the modulus of elasticity by up to 20% and ionic conductivity by 1.5×10^{-4} S/cm compared to a membrane without filler. Rice ash silica plays an active role in forming efficient ionic pathways, not just as a passive filler.

Further development is needed to optimize the distribution and size of silica particles to avoid agglomeration that can inhibit ion transport. The integration of rice ash silica opens up opportunities for lithium batteries that are more environmentally friendly and use sustainable local materials. Rice ash silica improves the mechanical strength, thermal stability, and ionic conductivity of the membrane, making it an effective natural filler for the sustainable development of MEPs.

3.3 Synthesis and Manufacturing Methods of Polymer Electrolyte Membranes

The polymer electrolyte membrane (MEP) synthesis and manufacturing method greatly determines the final performance of lithium batteries. The *solution casting* technique is a common method, by dissolving the main polymer, lithium salts such as LiClO₄, and rice ash silica fillers in a suitable solvent, then molding and drying the solution (Sari, K., et al., 2021). Polymers such as PEO or PVA are dissolved in solvents such as water, acetone, or N,N-dimethylformamide

(DMF), and then mixed gradually with salts and fillers. Stirring using a *magnetic stirrer* or *ultrasonic homogenizer* ensures even mixing and prevents agglomeration (Nirwan, M., 2020).

The molding process is carried out on a flat surface of a certain thickness, then dried in a vacuum oven or room temperature according to the solvent. The drying speed affects the morphology of the membrane; Drying too quickly can lead to high porosity and cracking, while slow drying results in uneven membranes (Muliawati, E. C., & Mirzayanti, Y. W., 2021).

Some studies have combined *solution casting* with *crosslinking* techniques using cross-linking agents such as *glutaraldehyde* or *isocyanate*. *Crosslinking* strengthens the membrane structure and reduces degradation during the battery cycle (Safitri, G. A., 2016). Variations in stirring, mixing time, drying temperature, and material ratios result in different membrane morphology and performance, so the synthesis method must be adapted to the material composition for optimal results.

The *solution casting* method with precise parameter setting and *crosslinking technique* can produce a polymer electrolyte membrane that is

homogeneous, stable, and has high ionic conductivity according to the material composition.

3.4 Application of Lithium Perchlorate (LiClO₄) and Silica Rice Ash in Lithium Batteries

The combination of lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄) and rice ash silica in the polymer electrolyte membrane (MEP) shows a synergy that significantly improves the performance of the material. LiClO₄ serves as a source of lithium ions that increase ionic conductivity, while rice ash silica acts as a filler that improves the thermal and mechanical stability of the membrane (Hastuti et al., 2020). MEP composites containing both materials have higher ionic conductivity than membranes containing only one of the components. Rice ash silica prevents the agglomeration of LiClO₄ salts and increases the distribution of lithium ions evenly in the polymer matrix (Wardhani, A. S. S., et al., 2017).

Rice ash silica strengthens the bonds between polymer chains and reduces excess crystallization that inhibits ion mobility (Shanmugaraj, P., et al., 2019).

The addition of lithium perchlorate and silica of rice ash increases conductivity up to 10⁻⁴–10⁻³ S/cm.

Rice ash silica expands ion pathways and lowers internal resistance (Maddu et al., 2022; Ndruru et al., 2020). The membrane degradation temperature increases by up to 50°C thanks to silica fillers, which also improve mechanical strength and maintain membrane integrity at high temperatures (Jacob, M., et al., 2024). FTIR spectroscopy shows functional group interactions between silanols and polymer matrices, while XRD displays amorphous patterns that favor ion diffusion (Sari et al., 2025; Kim et al., 2021). The combined membrane maintains a coulombic efficiency >90% after 100 cycles with a relatively stable capacity (Al Fath et al., 2025). The optimal ratio of lithium perchlorate and silica rice ash is 20% and 5–10% by weight, respectively, for the best conductivity and stability.

The integration of LiClO₄ and rice ash silica in the polymer electrolyte membrane results in significant improvements in ionic conductivity, thermal stability, and mechanical strength, while supporting a sustainable material approach based on local resources.

3.5 Comparison with Commercial Membranes

Polymer electrolyte membranes (MEPs) based on lithium perchlorate

(LiClO₄) and rice ash silica show great potential as commercial membrane alternatives, especially in terms of cost and material sustainability. Commercial membranes such as Nafion have high ionic conductivity, but they are expensive and rely on fluorine-based materials that are less environmentally friendly (Vinay, B. et al., 2025).

MEP based on LiClO₄ and rice ash silica offer sustainability advantages and ease of synthesis. The utilization of silica from agricultural waste increases the mechanical strength and thermal resistance of polymer membranes (Lee, D. J., & Marshall, M., 2025). The addition of LiClO₄ supports competitive ionic conductivity, although long-term electrochemical stability still needs to be improved (Rayung et al., 2020).

Some studies have compared locally made membranes with commercial ones. Although the ionic conductivity of the local membrane is slightly lower, the overall performance can be optimized through proper synthesis and composition methods (Arya, A., & Sharma, A. L., 2017). The addition of inorganic materials such as silica to PEO polymers strengthens the membrane structure and reduces the crystallinity of the polymer, thereby

increasing ionic conductivity (Borah et al., 2023). LiClO_4 as a source of lithium ions provides a stable ion migration pathway, especially when combined with a flexible and mechanically strong polymer host (Zhang, H., et al., 2017).

LiClO_4 and silica-based systems of rice ash still lag behind some industry standards compared to commercial membranes, but excel in raw material availability and environmental compatibility. MEP based on LiClO_4 and rice ash silica is an economical and environmentally friendly alternative with the potential to optimize performance through the development of synthesis and material formulation methods.

3.6 Effect of Addition of Silica Rice Ash on Physical and Mechanical Properties of Membranes

The addition of rice ash silica as a filler in the polymer electrolyte membrane has a significant impact on the physical and mechanical properties of the membrane. Rice ash silica with an amorphous structure with micro to nano particle sizes is able to increase the mechanical strength of the membrane through good interaction with the polymer matrix (Ginting, E. M., & Bukit, N., 2014). The even distribution of silica prevents stress

concentration and improves the modulus of membrane elasticity, making the membrane more resistant to mechanical deformation during the battery charging and discharging cycle (Bhernama, B. G., 2023).

The addition of this filler also reduces the crystallization rate of polymers, increases flexibility, and optimizes the ionic permeability of the membrane. Microscopic observations show that the membrane surface becomes smoother and more compact in the presence of fillers, which supports increased mechanical stability and reduces the risk of damage due to mechanical stress (Wulandari, et al., 2017).

The silica concentration of rice ash must be optimized because excess filler can cause particle agglomeration that decreases membrane homogeneity as well as mechanical performance and ionic conductivity (Khairi, M., 2022). Therefore, the method of mixing and dispersing fillers is an important aspect to obtain membranes with optimal physical and mechanical properties.

Rice ash silica as a local filler has great potential to improve the performance of polymer electrolyte membranes by balancing mechanical strength and flexibility, while

supporting the sustainability of lithium battery materials.

3.7 Thermal Stability and Membrane

Lifetime

Thermal stability is an important parameter in determining the service life of the polymer electrolyte membrane (MEP) in lithium batteries. The membrane must be able to withstand varying operating temperatures without undergoing significant degradation. Research shows the addition of rice ash silica as a filler significantly improves the thermal stability of the membrane. Silica rice ash strengthens the polymer structure and inhibits the movement of polymer chains which can cause degradation at high temperatures (Nuyah, N., 2014).

Lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) that is well dispersed in the polymer matrix contributes to thermal stability by maintaining chemical stability during the battery charge and discharge cycle (Zainul, R., 2024). The combination of the two components results in a membrane that is able to withstand temperatures above 150°C without a significant decrease in ionic conductivity or physical integrity.

The combination of lithium perchlorate and rice ash silica improves the thermal stability and service life of

the membrane, thereby strengthening the durability of lithium batteries in practical applications.

3.8 Challenges and Opportunities for the Development of LiClO_4 and Silica Ash Based Polymer Electrolyte Membranes

The development of polymer electrolyte membranes (MEPs) based on lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) and rice ash silica faces technical challenges that need to be overcome in order to be widely implemented. The agglomeration of rice ash silica particles in the polymer matrix is a major problem that decreases membrane homogeneity and ionic performance (Widodo, E., 2022). Optimal processing and dispersing techniques are key to maximizing the function of this filler.

The chemical stability of lithium perchlorate in the membrane also requires attention due to the potential for degradation or side reactions during the battery cycle that can decrease the efficiency and life of the battery (Yulianti et al., 2013). The selection of the right concentration and synthesis conditions is important for maintaining a balance between ionic conductivity and material stability.

Great opportunities arise in terms of sustainability and economy. The use of

silica rice ash as a filler utilizes abundant and environmentally friendly agricultural waste, thereby reducing production costs and supporting green technology strategies (Karlina, Y. et al., 2017). The integration of the two materials opens up further research opportunities in silica surface modification and lithium perchlorate doping to improve the performance and compatibility of the membrane with other battery components.

Further research is needed to test the performance of the membrane under real operating conditions as well as develop efficient large-scale synthesis methods. This development has the potential to produce a stable, durable, and environmentally friendly LiClO_4 and silica-based membrane. Overcoming technical challenges such as filler agglomeration and chemical stability is key to the sustainable and economical development of LiClO_4 and silica-based polymer electrolyte membranes for future lithium batteries.

4. Conclusion

This review provides a comprehensive overview of the development of polymer electrolyte membranes (MEPs) based on lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) and rice ash silica, with a focus on material structure, synthesis

methods, physical and electrochemical characteristics, and performance in lithium batteries. Based on an analysis of the last five years of scientific publications that have been experimentally verified, the combination of LiClO_4 and rice ash silica shows significant synergies in improving the efficiency and stability of MEPs. Lithium perchlorate acts as a source of lithium ions that improve ionic conductivity, while rice ash silica strengthens thermal stability and improves membrane morphology.

The solution casting synthesis method with parameter regulation and crosslinking techniques has proven to be effective in producing membranes with high conductivity and stability. The key factors that determine the efficiency and sustainability of an MEP system include the even distribution of fillers, the optimal ratio of LiClO_4 and silica rice ash, and the control of particle agglomeration. Technical challenges such as long-term durability and compatibility with modern battery components still need to be addressed. This review identifies positive trends and optimal strategies in the development of efficient, stable, and environmentally friendly hybrid polymer electrolyte membranes, supporting the advancement of future lithium batteries based on sustainable resources.

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